

Review

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[Nusrat Jahan](#)*

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Review

Drosophila Syntaxins in Intracellular Trafficking

Nusrat Jahan

Department of Biological Sciences, Northern Illinois University, DeKalb, IL 60115, USA;

z1906276@students.niu.edu

Abstract

Syntaxins are SNARE proteins that play essential roles in membrane fusion. In this review, I focus on *Drosophila* Syntaxins to provide a valuable insight in understanding the conserved principle of SNARE mediated membrane fusion in intracellular trafficking. This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of how individual *Drosophila* Syntaxins contribute to distinct intracellular pathways, including secretory/Golgi trafficking, endocytic/endosomal sorting, and autophagy/endolysosomal fusion pathway. My studies reveal that each *Drosophila* Syntaxin executes a unique and essential function within intracellular transport networks.

Keywords: *Drosophila*; intracellular trafficking; membrane fusion; SNARE; Syntaxin

1. Introduction

Intracellular trafficking is a well-regulated process that controls the membrane dynamic to facilitate the movements of proteins, lipids and different macromolecules in the subcellular structure. The correct movement of these macromolecules is essential to maintain tissue homeostasis and biogenesis. Deviation of this process can lead to pathophysiological conditions [1]. In eukaryotic cell the communication or exchange of macromolecules between membrane bound organelles occurred through vesicle mediated trafficking [2]. The general process of vesicle mediated trafficking begins with vesicle formation from the donor compartment membrane. The newly formed vesicles then move toward their destination, where they dock to the target membrane and undergo membrane fusion to release the cargo into the target compartment [2,3].

Fusion step of vesicle transport is mediated by a family of proteins called SNARE (Soluble N-ethylmaleimide-sensitive-factor Attachment Protein Receptor) [4-7]. Each of the family members has conserved SNARE motif [2]. Functionally, SNAREs were classified into two categories [2,7]. If SNARE is localized at the donor compartment, then it is known as v-SNARE (vesicle membrane SNARE) [2,7]. If a SNARE is localized at the acceptor compartment membrane, then it is known as t-SNARE (target membrane SNARE) [2,7]. However, this kind of classification is not helpful if there is homotypic fusion or if the SNARE is involved in two directions of transport (anterograde trafficking and retrograde trafficking) [2]. This limitation is resolved by adopting the structural Q/R classification, which provides a stable and universally applicable framework for describing SNARE identity and organization [2]. SNARE proteins are categorized based on the type of amino acid they contribute to the central "0 layer" of the four-helix bundle involved in membrane fusion. This structural feature was first revealed through crystallographic studies of the neuronal SNARE complex [8]. The residue at the 0 layer can be either a glutamine (Q) or an arginine (R). This single positional difference is the key element used to classify SNARE proteins into Q or R groups in comparative structural studies [9]. Q SNAREs are further separated into Qa, Qb, and Qc categories based on the specific position each helix occupies within the bundle [10]. SNAREs that contribute an arginine at the 0 layer are grouped as R SNAREs [11]. A complete and functional fusion complex always contains one Qa SNARE, one Qb SNARE, one Qc SNARE, and one R SNARE (Figure 1). These proteins assemble into the characteristic four-helix structure required for membrane fusion. Experiments have shown that only QabcR combinations assemble into a stable, fusion competent

complex [5]. Together these four helices produce a tightly packed and highly conserved coiled coil structure that brings two membranes into close proximity to promote fusion, a mechanism supported by both biochemical and structural studies [12]. This Q/Qa Qb Qc/R system presented as a fundamental and evolutionarily conserved organizational pattern that explains how different SNARE proteins cooperate to mediate membrane fusion across diverse intracellular trafficking pathways [13]. Owing to this evolutionary conservation, genetically tractable organism such as *Drosophila* is an ideal organism to study the role of SNARE proteins in regulation of intracellular trafficking.

Figure 1. SNARE complex formation. (Left panel) A vesicle is positioned near the target/plasma membrane. The vesicle membrane contains the v-SNARE (blue), while the plasma membrane contains the t-SNAREs (red, green and orange). (Right panel) Assembly of the trans-SNARE complex brings the vesicle and plasma membranes into close apposition. v-SNARE on the vesicle interacts with t-SNARE on the plasma membrane. The SNAREs shown here include v- and t-SNAREs of the Qa, Qb, Qc, and R classes.

Drosophila is an excellent model Organism to study intracellular trafficking because the core trafficking components are conserved. The fruit fly also contains cell and tissue types such as photoreceptors, follicle cells, and imaginal discs. These tissues undergo massive and highly organized membrane transport during development. As a result, defects in trafficking machinery become easy to visualize when key proteins are disrupted [14,15]. In addition, the *Drosophila* system offers a wide range of well-characteristic markers. It also provides genetically tractable platforms that enable precise analysis of Golgi function, vesicle accumulation, and protein transport defects in living tissue. Together, these tools support detailed investigation of how specific proteins contribute to membrane dynamics [14]. Because epithelial tissues and imaginal discs can be imaged *in vivo*, researchers can directly observe how intracellular trafficking maintains cell polarity and tissue architecture, and how disruptions in these processes lead to abnormal protein accumulation or signaling defects [15]. Finally, the fly enables highly controlled gene knockdown and clean loss of function mutant generation, making it possible to track the consequences of removing individual trafficking components in specific tissues and to dissect their roles in maintaining normal cellular and developmental function [14–16].

Consistent with its utility as a model organism, analysis of *Drosophila* genome indicates that *Drosophila* SNARE protein family members are homologue to vertebrate [17]. *Drosophila* has 25 SNARE family members involved in diverse intracellular trafficking pathways. The classification of *Drosophila* SNAREs based on QR system is summarized in Table 1. Among SNAREs, Syntaxins constitute a major class of Q-SNAREs that serve as key organizers of SNARE complex assembly.

Drosophila has total 10 Syntaxin members. Some Syntaxins belong to Qa SNARE subgroup (Syntaxin1/Syntaxin1A, Syntaxin4, Syntaxin5, Syntaxin7, Syntaxin13, Syntaxin16, Syntaxin17, Syntaxin18) (Table 1). Some Syntaxins belong to Qc SNARE subgroup (Syntaxin6, Syntaxin8) (Table 1). Given their central role in membrane fusion, focusing on *Drosophila* Syntaxin protein can provide a valuable insight in understanding the conserved principle of SNARE mediated membrane fusion in intracellular trafficking.

Table 1. Classification of *Drosophila* SNARE genes. The table summarizes the *Drosophila* SNARE gene family, showing the total number of genes, the major types (R-SNARE and Q-SNARE), their subtypes (Qa, Qb, Qc, Qbc), the individual gene names, and the number of genes in each category. This provides a comprehensive overview of the SNARE gene hierarchy in *Drosophila*.

SNARE Type (<i>Drosophila</i>)	Subtype	Gene Names	Number of Genes
Total SNARE	—	—	25
R-SNARE	—	Sec22, Syb, Vamp7, Ykt6, nSyb	5
Q-SNARE	—	—	20
	Qa-SNARE	Syntaxin1 (Syntaxin1A), Syntaxin4, Syntaxin5, Syntaxin7, Syntaxin13, Syntaxin16, Syntaxin17, Syntaxin18	8
	Qb-SNARE	Gos28, Membrin, Sec20, Vti1a, Vti1b	5
	Qc-SNARE	Bet1, Syntaxin6, Syntaxin8, Use1	4
	Qbc-SNARE	Snap24, Snap25, Snap29	3

In this review, postsynaptic membrane *Drosophila* Syntaxins such as Syntaxin4 and Syntaxin18 are excluded. The focus is limited to Syntaxins functioning within intracellular secretory, endosomal, and autophagic pathways rather than postsynaptic membrane trafficking. I synthesize findings from genetic, cellular, and molecular studies. I aim to provide a comprehensive overview of how individual Syntaxins contribute to distinct intracellular pathways, including secretory/Golgi trafficking, endocytic/endosomal sorting, and autophagy/endolysosomal fusion pathway. Table 2 presents the full set of *Drosophila* Syntaxins together with the titles of the papers that describe their intracellular trafficking functions. The insights from these papers are synthesized in this review whenever they relate to the trafficking role of a given *Drosophila* Syntaxin. The primary aim of this review is to summarize the functional specialization of *Drosophila* Syntaxins, integrating current knowledge across different trafficking pathways while highlighting uncharacterized Syntaxins and underexplored areas. By identifying these knowledge gaps, I aim to provide a roadmap for future research into SNARE-mediated intracellular trafficking and its impact on development and tissue organization.

Table 2. *Drosophila* Syntaxins and representative studies categorized by intracellular trafficking pathway. Information includes syntaxin name, FlyBase ID, paper title, pathway classification, and DOI link. The table lists each Syntaxin, representative studies included in this review. Postsynaptic Syntaxins (Syntaxin4 and Syntaxin18) are included for completeness but are not discussed in the main text of this review. Syntaxins with no reported *Drosophila* trafficking studies (e.g., Syntaxin6, Syntaxin8, Syntaxin16) are included for completeness, and the corresponding table entries are left blank.

No.	<i>Drosophila</i> Syntaxin	FlyBase ID	Paper Title	Authors	Intracellular Trafficking Pathway	DOI Link
1	Syntaxin1 (Syntaxin1A)	FBgn0013343	The Synaptic Protein Syntaxin1 Is Required for Cellularization of <i>Drosophila</i> Embryos	Burgess et al.	Secretory	https://doi.org/10.1083/jcb.138.4.861
2	Syntaxin1 (Syntaxin1A)	FBgn0013343	Efficient EGFR signaling and dorsal ventral axis patterning requires syntaxin dependent Gurken trafficking	Tian et al.	Secretory	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ydbio.2012.10.029
3	Syntaxin4	FBgn0024980	The postsynaptic t-SNARE Syntaxin4 controls traffic of Neuroligin1 and Synaptotagmin4	Harris et al.	Postsynaptic Membrane	https://doi.org/10.7554/elife.13881
4	Syntaxin5	FBgn0011708	The roles of Syx5 in Golgi morphology and Rhodopsin transport in <i>Drosophila</i> photoreceptors	Satoh et al.	Secretory	https://doi.org/10.1242/bio.020958
5	Syntaxin6	FBgn0037084	—	—	—	—
6	Syntaxin7	FBgn0267849	Endocytic control of epithelial polarity and proliferation in <i>Drosophila</i>	Lu & Bilder	Endocytic	https://doi.org/10.1038/ncb1324
7	Syntaxin8	FBgn0036643	—	—	—	—
8	Syntaxin13	FBgn0036341	Syntaxin13 is required for autophagosome maturation	Lu et al.	Endolysosomal	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molcel.2013.08.041
9	Syntaxin16	FBgn0031106	—	—	—	—
10	Syntaxin17	FBgn0035540	Autophagosomal Syntaxin17-dependent lysosomal degradation maintains neuronal function in <i>Drosophila</i>	Takáts et al.	Endolysosomal	https://doi.org/10.1083/jcb.201211160
11	Syntaxin18	FBgn0039212	Postsynaptic membrane addition depends on the Discs-Large-interacting t-SNARE Gtaxin	Gorczyca	Postsynaptic Membrane	https://doi.org/10.1523/jneurosci.3160-06.2007

2. Section Title

2.1. Secretory Pathway Syntaxins

In *Drosophila melanogaster*, Syntaxin1 (Syntaxin1A) and Syntaxin5 represent key t-SNAREs involved in secretory pathway. These Syntaxins orchestrate membrane fusion events that are critical for developmental morphogenesis and cellular homeostasis. Below, I synthesize the specific contributions of *Drosophila* Syntaxin1 and Syntaxin5 to secretory trafficking.

Syntaxin1

Syntaxin1, a t-SNARE, localized at the presynaptic membrane, plays an essential role in neurotransmitter release [18,19]. Previous studies showed that Syntaxin1 binds Synaptobrevin/VAMP, SNAP25, Synaptotagmin, and nsec1 to form a protein complex required for vesicle fusion at synaptic terminals [20–22]. Loss of Syntaxin1 eliminates both evoked and spontaneous neurotransmitter release. However, vesicles were found physically docked at the presynaptic membrane. These demonstrate that synaptic vesicles can reach and dock at the membrane but cannot fuse without Syntaxin1 [23,24]. These findings suggest that Syntaxin1 is necessary for membrane fusion step of synaptic vesicle exocytosis [23,24]. Because of the highly specialized of synaptic terminals, these results left open a question: whether Syntaxin1 necessity for membrane fusion is tied to all cell types, or its function is specific to neurons.

Burgess et al. (1997) reported that Syntaxin1 is required for membrane addition during *Drosophila* early embryonic cellularization process [25]. These findings suggest that Syntaxin1 function in membrane fusion is global. At the onset of cellularization during cycle 14, Syntaxin1 appears along the emerging lateral cell surfaces and the invaginating cleavage furrows. During this period, vesicles need to fuse with the surface membrane to supply membrane for invagination. Embryos with reduced maternal and zygotic Syntaxin1 levels develop large acellular patches lacking membrane invagination and proper actin organization. These suggest that vesicles reach the cortex but cannot fuse to extend the plasma membrane during cellularization. Burgess et al. provide evidence that Syntaxin1 is required for membrane fusion, supporting the notion that Syntaxin1 serves as a global mediator of membrane fusion events. However, this work highlights few gaps [25]. Syntaxin1 functions as the target membrane SNARE, but successful vesicle fusion requires a SNARE protein complex comprising four different SNAREs. The specific binding partners of Syntaxin1 during cellularization have not been identified. While Syntaxin1 is necessary for membrane fusion at invaginating furrows, the broader mechanism including how actin or microtubule networks guide vesicles to their targets and how the cell makes sure enough vesicles arrive to build the growing lateral membrane remains yet to be understood. Additional research is necessary to fill these gaps in our understanding.

The foundational understanding of Syntaxin1's role as a global mediator in membrane fusion events provided an essential framework for subsequent studies demonstrating its function within more specialized intracellular trafficking pathways. Tian et al. (2013) reported that Syntaxin1 is associated with the Golgi membrane and is required for the transportation of Gurken protein containing vesicles along microtubules to the dorsal anterior destination in the oocyte [16]. Evidence for this comes from observations that Syntaxin1 localizes to punctate structures that partially overlap with Rab6 and the Golgi marker (GalT). Loss of Syntaxin1 results in Gurken and Rab6 becoming trapped in enlarged vesicles instead of reaching the dorsal anterior cortex. Syntaxin1 functions within a Golgi-associated, Rab6-dependent trafficking pathway. This pathway is responsible for delivering Gurken containing vesicles to the dorsal anterior region. Syntaxin1 is then required to ensure that the vesicles are properly targeted and successfully fuse with the membrane. Together, the data show that Syntaxin1 has functions beyond classical membrane fusion. It is required for the accurate delivery of Gurken protein carrying, Rab6-positive vesicles to the dorsal-anterior cortex. At this destination, vesicle fusion must occur to enable proper EGFR activation [16]. While the study provides significant

findings, Tian et al. leaves multiple avenues open for future investigation. Genetic and imaging evidence indicates that Syntaxin1 and Rab6 operate within the same trafficking pathway. However, the study could not detect direct physical interaction between them. As a result, the molecular interface responsible for transferring Gurken-containing vesicles from Rab6 positive carriers to the Syntaxin1 containing target membrane remains unclear. This suggests the existence of intermediary effectors that have not yet been identified. Another unresolved question involves the true identity of the Gurken transporting vesicle. The study shows that these compartments contain Rab6 and Golgi markers. However, their precise origin whether from a specific Golgi subdomain, the trans Golgi network, or a recycling endosomal route remains undefined.

Together, these studies define Syntaxin1 as a global fusion factor within multiple intracellular trafficking pathways. While Syntaxin1 does not control vesicle directionality, trafficking fails without Syntaxin1 because vesicles that reach their destination cannot undergo fusion with the target membrane. Thus, in *Drosophila*, Syntaxin1 acts as a core component of vesicle target fusion in processes as diverse as neuronal exocytosis, epithelial membrane expansion during cellularization, and polarized secretion of developmental signals during oogenesis.

Syntaxin5

Whereas Syntaxin1 plays role in late secretory pathway, Syntaxin5 activity is centered at the beginning of the secretory pathway, ensuring proper ER-derived vesicle fusion and early golgi organization. Satoh et al. (2016) defines Syntaxin5 as an essential cis Golgi t-SNARE for early secretory pathway that enables biogenesis and polarized membrane trafficking of rhodopsin protein in *Drosophila* photoreceptors [14]. Evidence for this comes from the observation that Syntaxin5 localizes specifically to Rab1 positive ER derived vesicles and GM130 marked cis Golgi cisternae. Syntaxin5 deficient photoreceptors accumulate massive clusters of unfused COPII vesicles between the ER and Golgi accompanied by dilation and fragmentation of cisternae. Additionally, loss of Syntaxin5 prevents Rh1 cargo from reaching any of the three plasma membrane domains. These cargos do not accumulate cytoplasmically but instead are rapidly degraded through ER associated degradation (ERAD). Thus, demonstrating that the trafficking block occurs upstream of Golgi maturation. The data show that Syntaxin5 is required for fusion of COPII vesicles to form and maintain cis Golgi cisternae. Rh1 successfully exits the ER but cannot progress past the cis Golgi in *syntaxin5* mutants. This pattern indicates that Syntaxin5 operates at an earlier secretory step than Rab6, whose mutants retain intact cis Golgi structure and selectively disrupt apical sorting, diverting Rh1 to multivesicular bodies instead of ERAD [14]. Although Syntaxin5 is clearly required to fuse ER derived vesicles with the cis Golgi, the mechanistic sequence by which it binds and organizes vesicle SNAREs such as Sec22 and Bet1 is not yet clear. Further work is needed to determine how this SNARE assembly process is regulated in the native context of *Drosophila* photoreceptors. The implication of these findings is that Syntaxin5 functions as a gatekeeper for cis Golgi biogenesis, ensuring that polarized intracellular trafficking pathways can operate downstream in the secretory system. Disruption at this earliest step causes a collapse of trafficking that depends on proper early Golgi function.

2.2. Endocytic/Endosomal Trafficking Syntaxin

In *Drosophila melanogaster*, Syntaxin7 (Avalanche, Avl) represents the Endocytic/Endosomal Trafficking Syntaxin. Syntaxin7 coordinates endosomal fusion processes that are critical for maintaining epithelial polarity, membrane turnover, and overall cellular organization. Below, I summarize the roles of *Drosophila* Syntaxin7 in endosomal trafficking.

Syntaxin7

Whereas Syntaxin1 and Syntaxin5 function in exocytic or secretory transport, In *Drosophila*, Syntaxin7 serves as the principal t-SNARE mediating early endosomal fusion. Lu and Bilder (2005)

demonstrate that Syntaxin7 protein localizes specifically to early endosomes [15]. Syntaxin7 displays strong colocalization with early endosome markers, Rab5-GFP and the 2xFYVE PI3P reporter. Syntaxin7 shows minimal overlaps with markers of late endosomes (Rab7), recycling endosomes (Rab11), or the Golgi. They further show that in wild type epithelia, surface proteins such as Notch and Crumbs (Crb) rapidly enter Syntaxin7 positive endosomes and subsequently progress toward degradation. However, in the *syntaxin7* null mutant epithelia, these cargos fail to internalize. As a result, they accumulate persistently at the plasma membrane and in peripheral non endosomal compartments. Importantly, *rab5* null mutants phenocopy the *syntaxin7* mutant trafficking defects and shows the same failure to move Notch and Crb into early endosomes. In *syntaxin7* mutant, protein remains at the membrane rather than entering endosomes for degradation. Together, these data establish that Syntaxin7 is required for entry of internalized cargo into the early endosome. Syntaxin7 functions at or slightly upstream of Rab5 dependent early endosomal fusion. It is required for internalizing apical surface proteins toward downstream endocytic sorting and degradation. These findings indicate that Syntaxin7 plays role in a specific and indispensable fusion step at early endosomes [15].

Within Syntaxin proteins mediated intracellular trafficking pathways, the Lu and Bilder study assigns a distinct role to Syntaxin7 at the initial fusion step of the endocytic route. Syntaxin5 mediates ER to Golgi fusion, and Syntaxin1 supports exocytic delivery. In contrast, Syntaxin7 functions at the early endosome, where it is required for the fusion events that allow internalized transmembrane proteins to enter the early endosomal compartment. In *syntaxin7* mutants, these proteins fail to appear in early endosomal puncta, indicating a block in early endosomal entry. These results position Syntaxin7 as a Syntaxin that defines the entry step into the endocytic pathway, thereby determining whether internalized cargo proceeds toward recycling or degradation. Although this study defines Syntaxin7 function in early endosomal entry, it does not determine which SNAREs make complex with Syntaxin7 during this step. Determining these missing components represents an important direction for future research.

2.3. Autophagy/Endolysosomal Fusion Syntaxins

Beyond their functions in secretion and endosomal transport, certain *Drosophila* Syntaxin proteins also participate in the autophagy/endolysosomal pathway. In this section, I focus on Syntaxin13 and Syntaxin17 for their role in autophagy/endolysosomal pathway.

Syntaxin13

Lu et al. (2013) identified Syntaxin13 is an important intracellular trafficking protein that helps early autophagy membranes mature into proper autophagosomes [26]. When Syntaxin13 is reduced in cells, early autophagy markers such as LC3 and Atg5 build up, large LC3 positive vesicles accumulate, and the autophagy process becomes blocked before autophagosomes can close. Syntaxin13 normally sits on early autophagy membranes called phagophores. Loss of Syntaxin13 leads to disorganized, multilayered membrane structures. ESCRT-III regulates the final membrane sealing step. When ESCRT-III function is compromised, LC3-positive multilamellar structures accumulate and become enriched with Syntaxin13. Syntaxin13 organizes early autophagy membranes to bring them to a state competent for the ESCRT-III dependent sealing of unclosed phagophores. This highlights that the autophagosome maturation relies on proper Syntaxin13 mediated trafficking. Syntaxin13 demonstrates that specific Syntaxin protein functions not only to membrane transport but also to regulating organelle transition states, such as the conversion of the phagophore into the autophagosome. The study shows that Syntaxin13 and Vti1a form complex to orchestrate early autophagy related to membrane trafficking and phagophore maturation [26]. However, the identity of the additional SNARE components that assemble with this pair to form a complete SNARE complex remains undefined and represents an important area for future investigation.

Syntaxin17

Takáts et al. (2013) identified Syntaxin17 as a key Qa SNARE that functions within the lysosomal system by regulating the final membrane fusion step required for autolysosome formation in *Drosophila* [27]. Their work demonstrates that Syntaxin17 is recruited specifically to the outer membrane of fully formed autophagosomes. Syntaxin17 forms a trans-SNARE complex with SNAP-29 (Qbc-SNARE) and VAMP7 (R-SNARE) to mediate autophagosome fusion through two established entry routes into the lysosomal system. Fusion of autophagosome with late endosomes generate amphisomes. Direct fusion autophagosome with lysosomes to form autolysosomes. Both of these ultimately deliver autophagic cargo into the lysosomal degradative compartment. To monitor this process, the authors used Atg8a, a lipidated LC3 homolog that stably associates with the autophagosomal membrane. Atg8a positive puncta is a well-established indicator of autophagosome abundance [28]. As autophagosomes successfully fuse with lysosomes, the resulting autolysosomes become brightly LysoTracker positive, reflecting the dye's selective accumulation in low pH lysosomal compartments [29,30]. In addition, the selective autophagy receptor p62 (Ref(2)P in *Drosophila*) binds ubiquitinated cargo and is degraded only after autophagosome–lysosome fusion. Thus, the accumulation of p62 serves as a reliable biochemical indicator of impaired autophagic flux, reflecting defective lysosomal degradation [31,32]. Loss of any member of the Syntaxin17–SNAP29–VAMP7 complex results in a complete block of autophagic flux, reflected by the accumulation of Atg8a positive autophagosomes, the absence of LysoTracker positive autolysosomes, and the buildup of p62 aggregates. Together, these findings demonstrate that Syntaxin17 is essential for delivering autophagic cargo into the lysosomal degradative compartment [27]. Although Takáts et al. establish Syntaxin17 as the Syntaxin required for autophagosome fusion with late endosomes and lysosomes, major questions remain regarding the mechanisms of Syntaxin17 recruitment, and the identity of upstream tethering factors. Syntaxin13 and Syntaxin17 operate at sequential checkpoints in the autophagy-lysosomal pathway. Syntaxin13 controls the maturation and closure of phagophores. Syntaxin17 governs the subsequent fusion of completed autophagosomes with late endosomes and lysosomes. Together creates an integrated, stepwise Syntaxins regulated system for lysosomal degradation.

3. Knowledge Gaps and future Directions

Although the functions of multiple *Drosophila* Syntaxins in secretory, endosomal, and autophagic transport are well defined, several members including Syntaxin6, Syntaxin8, and Syntaxin16 have yet to be characterized in the context of intracellular trafficking. To the best of our knowledge, no published studies have provided functional data defining the intracellular trafficking roles of *Drosophila* Syntaxin6, Syntaxin8, or Syntaxin16. This absence of functional characterization suggests that our understanding of SNARE mediated membrane trafficking is incomplete. Elucidating the involvement of these uncharacterized Syntaxins in intracellular trafficking could reveal novel mechanisms and expand the current framework of Syntaxin mediated membrane fusion.

4. Conclusions

Drosophila Syntaxins constitute a diverse group of Q-SNARE proteins involved in membrane fusion. Through their roles in the secretory, endosomal, and autophagic pathway, they collectively regulate intracellular trafficking. Syntaxins1 and Syntaxin5 mediate essential fusion events in the early secretory system, while Syntaxin7 plays role in endosomal trafficking. Autophagy related Syntaxin13 and Syntaxin17 support autophagosome formation and lysosomal fusion, thereby supporting intracellular degradation process. Despite these advances, major gaps persist: the roles of Syntaxin6, Syntaxin8, and Syntaxin16 remain undefined, and key mechanistic details of SNARE complex assembly, cargo recognition, and regulatory interactions are still poorly understood. Addressing these questions will deepen our understanding of how conserved fusion machinery adapts across cellular contexts. Collectively, *Drosophila* Syntaxins provide a powerful model for

dissecting fundamental principles of SNARE mediated membrane fusion while elucidating how membrane trafficking influences development and physiology.

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